

BUDDHA SERIES PAINTING: A REVIEW

-DR. DHARMENDRA KUMAR SINGH

The light, that chiefly dominates the world, is ‘The Light of the World’ and ‘The Light of Asia’. The former stands for Jesus Christ whereas the latter, for Lord Buddha. For the upliftment and enlightenment of mortality, both of them did their best in their ways at their age. They lived their life for others. Consequently, they have been the star of the people’s eyes even today. The result is that, from time to time, both the writers and the artists respect and adore them with the fresh flowers of their creations in their concerned till date. In this queue, also comes the name of **Dr. Narendra Singh**, a renowned Professor of the Department of Drawing and Painting, at **MHPG College Moradabad**, affiliated to **MJPRU Bareilly**, U.P., the Republic of Bharat. Catching the spirit of the time (Zeitgeist), Last Year, he demonstrated the installation of ‘**Buddha Series Paintings**’ at **Jahangir Art Gallery, Mumbai** from 13 to 19 Dec. 2022.

The message that gold can never be old is true to his creative world, i.e., Buddha, the gold, can never be old—I mean out of fashion—is the message that this series of paintings seems to be imparting. Buddha, the kernel of tangible life, is the need of time and beyond. As a reviewer, when I watched this series of paintings, neither I could not check, then, myself of thinking the Russia and Ukraine war, nor now, can’t of the war between Hamas and Israel army, i.e., this installation of art catches the spirit of such time as is trembling, shivering, and shuddering

with the apprehension of another “Little Boy” and “Fat Man”—

the impending third World War. The title of the installation art “Buddha Series Paintings” presents such a deed of the doer that is adequately full in illustrating and representing all the fancies and imaginations as to be believable and making it never anything less than three-dimensional. Tempting the eyes of the spectators in the exhibition, it suggests that old is still gold and like Buddha, gives the message of sustaining amity among the moss without any perplexity in every condition and situation of life. Besides, these paintings suggest being free like the Light of Asia from all temporal things to get true knowledge that may be part of enlightenment, I think.

This installation of art is a series of about 21 paintings on acrylic canvas that presents Lord Buddha in various *MUDRAS* (gestures) signifying the sentiments within sentiments both of the painter and the painted. As a whole, the theme with which this series deals, is love, peace, and enlightenment of which this world in which we dwell, is now hungry and thirsty. The message that this series of paintings impart to the world is that Buddha, for being most relevant is the only solution to all worldly problems. From each and every foreign policy to the values and morals existing in this new Bharat is directly or indirectly affected by him as a whole. The installation of Buddha series paintings offers a new perspective on the history and revival of Buddhism in the India of *AMRIT KAAL*.

The colour of the paintings also tells a lot. Dr. Singh has applied various shades in the series of these paintings. His colouring scheme has its chemistry. It depicts and describes the subject well. As an adept artist—painter—, Dr. Singh has highly utilized his knowledge of hues to portray mood, light, depth, and point of view (POV) in this series. It is the coloration that speeds the visual

search improves object recognition and enhances the meaning to convey the structure to establish the identity. His use of various hues symbolizes his thoughts and improves their usability to communicate his mood with the mood of the spectators. His use of white colour tells the tale of cutting the delusion of ignorance and turning it into the wisdom of reality; pink, innocence and burning passion; Yellow, of transforming pride into wisdom of sameness when visualized in meditation; green, of transforming jealousy into the wisdom of discernment; red, of transforming the delusion of attachment into the wisdom of discernment; saffron, of strength and courage, and sacrifice; black, of grief and ignorance; and blue, of infinite space. The use of the dark tincture stands for his depth and mysticism that is beyond the common sense of human computation whereas the light colour, signifies the lighter things which are worldly.

The first three paintings that in this art gallery allure the eyes most are 'Buddha with Flutes'.

These paintings remind lord Krishna who enchanted the world and its creatures with the melodious music of his flute. Like Lord Krishna, Lord Buddha also has enchanted and enchants the world with the heart-penetrating melodious sound of his preachings and set the people free from the tussles of pain and grief that dominate their lives. The pattern of these three paintings resembles lots, but colours, for the commoners, tell another tale in baffling ways.

Next comes the painting of Buddha with the lotus holding differently. In the first painting, it is put before him; in the second, in the

right hand; and the third, in the same hand, but in the smelling condition, and the background, the semi-darkness with or without the falling of the sacred *PEOPLE* leaves enhances the curiosity of the watchers. Lotus suggests enlightenment, mental purity, and spiritual perfection associated with the pacification of one's nature whereas the falling leaves of the sacred tree suggest the ceaseless flow of knowledge, love, and karma for the betterment of the world as a whole. The continual glow of the face and the halo behind it reminds the lunar or solar eclipse in which the moon or sun in turn has to lose its heavenly light. It seems, as these paintings seem to be suggesting to maintain serenity of mind and calmness of heart even in the hours of perplexity caused by the world in which we are to continue our existence and to prove our essence that depends on the existence of our choices.

Next comes two pieces of painting in which the painter—Dr. Singh—has painted Buddha, as a 'Sweating

Buddha'. Here sweat symbolizes his toil in life done to set the mass free from the cycle of birth and death with the help of *NIRVANA* or blowing out or quenching. The colour of the painting—red—alters the colour of the spectator's face making them think and think.

After the paintings of the 'Sweating Buddha', comes the painting of 'Preaching Buddha'. In it,

Buddha, the Light of Asia, has been painted or presented in preaching

and blessing mode as well, but the difference in the colouring of the background suggests that for the world's well-being and betterment,

it (world) needs (the preachings of)

Buddha in both conditions—of light and darkness as well, i.e., even amid the chaos, Buddha, the Boddhisatva, is the need of time. He is an opportunity. He is a possibility for one and all. His teachings comprise the four decent truths—the truth of the sorrow or suffering, the truth of the roots of suffering, the truth of the end of suffering, and the truth of the pathway leading to the end of suffering, i.e., such reflection of the colored suffering colored me to think and rethink about these paintings to which I am reviewing, here, after a year of the installation.

In the final group of Paintings, Buddha is presented in the mode of getting enlightenment, in the mode of preaching, and finally in the sleeping mode. This trio of paintings seems to be suggesting

the lessons to the holy heroes to attain true knowledge not only to teach the populace but also to attain self-satisfaction—that in the dictionary of *SANATANISM* stands for *PARMANAND*— after attaining enlightenment as well.

The sum and substance of this series of paintings is love, action, and purity—spirituality— which the world badly needs today. Without them, this world seems to be a wasteland without its Godot. This series of paintings presents the various gestures of Lord Buddha especially of face and palm which signify the enlightened and benevolent Buddha brimming with peace and knowledge. He is presented in such a pose as he is scattering the gems of spirituality to the world. The halo, which is reflected mostly in all paintings, reflects the light residing within the soul and the waves which arise from his countenance present his perfectness as a whole.

Kudos to Dr. Singh for giving such a powerful and relevant message to the world through the installation of the ‘Buddha Series Paintings’. The world, standing on the verge of the third impending global war, misses Buddha a lots. He is the need of today. And Dr. Singh seems to be filling this need through his installation. Here, his every work of art, silently tells all the tales of the enlightened head—I mean of Buddha— to the great hands and heads of the world. In the portrayals of Buddha, he is present. His personality gently becomes impersonal and starts to deliver the silent message of Buddha to the world. Each painting is brimming with his thoughts, feelings, and emotions. His paintings not only present the outward appearance of the things but also their inward significance. The history and mystery that it evokes are so cardinal that without them the world would not exist. A picture is worth a thousand words...little drops of ink with a million thinks— thoughts....**Note:** All the paintings enclosed in this review are painted by Dr. Narendra Singh.

Bio:- Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Singh is a Lecturer of English literature and Assistant Professor of Existentialism in the Novels of Thomas Hardy together with Philosophical Perspective of Existentialism: A Critical Evaluation of the Selected Indian English Novels and Novelists at MHPG College Moradabad, affiliated to **MJPRU Bareilly** U.P., the Republic of Bharat. Creative as well as critical writing is his passion.